

A NEW APPROACH TO THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF PEDAGOGUE

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Annotation: This article is devoted to the main concepts of competence, definitions given by various experts, and approaches that contribute to the development of professional competences of the pedagogue.

Keywords: competence, professional competence, special or professional competence, social competence, extreme competence, innovative, creative.

One of the important requirements for the organization of modern education is to achieve high results in a short time without spending too much mental and physical effort. Formation of certain activity skills and competencies based on the delivery of certain theoretical knowledge to students in a short time, control of their activities, assessment of the level of theoretical and practical knowledge acquired by them requires high pedagogical skills from the teacher, a new approach to the educational process requires.

According to the "Concept of the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on October 8, 2019, increasing the level of coverage of higher education in the country, highly qualified, creative and systematic based on international standards It is necessary to create the necessary conditions for the training of personnel who can make independent decisions, to demonstrate their intellectual abilities, and to develop them as morally competent individuals. Training of specialists who can meet the requirements of the times, improving education and all its structural structures based on the requirements of the state is one of the urgent issues.

It is important to increase the intellectual potential of teachers of various specialties in the retraining and advanced training courses of pedagogues of higher education organizations, to familiarize them closely with innovative educational technologies to enrich their worldviews. As a result of the reforms implemented in the development of the material and technical support of education in our republic, the creation of an information-educational environment, the development of information resources, the improvement of the methods of their use in the educational process, the international education of students and teachers The possibilities of using land resources are expanding. At this point, each specialist is required to have professional competence and to increase it consistently. So what is competence?

What qualities are reflected in the basis of professional competence? It is necessary for the teacher to be able to highlight the qualities of competence. [1].

"**Competency**" (incl. "competencye" - "ability") - effective use of theoretical knowledge in activity, high-level professional qualification, skill and ability to demonstrate.

"**Competence**" as a pedagogical category entered the field of education as a result of psychological scientific research. From a psychological point of view, competence is "how a specialist behaves in non-traditional situations, unexpected (non-standard) situations, engages in communication, takes a new path in interactions with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses conflicting information, "Let's come to a plan of movement in the consistently developing and complex processes". Based on this, the category of professional competence is explained as follows.

Professional competence - provides for the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and qualifications necessary for professional activity by a specialist and their practical application at a high level.

Professional competence is not the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but integrative knowledge in each independent direction.

and implies the mastery of actions. Also, "competence" requires constant enrichment of professional knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it, and being able to apply it in one's work.

Professional competence is evident in the following cases:

Specialist with professional competence:

constantly enriches his knowledge;

learns new information; deeply understands the requirements of the era;

seeks new knowledge;

processes them and uses them effectively in his practical work.

The following qualities are reflected on the basis of professional competence:

Social competence is the ability to be active in social relations, acquire skills, and be able to communicate with subjects in professional activities.

Special competence is preparation for organization of professional-pedagogical activity, rational solution of professional-pedagogical tasks, realistic assessment of activity results, consistent development of knowledge, skills and competence, based on this competence psychological, methodical, informational, creative, innovative and communicative competence are prominent. They express the following content:

a) psychological competence - the ability to create a healthy psychological environment in the pedagogical process, to organize positive communication with students and other participants of the educational process, to be able to understand and eliminate various negative psychological conflicts in time;

b) methodical competence - methodologically reasonable organization of the pedagogical process, correct determination of the forms of educational or educational activity, method

and to be able to choose tools according to the purpose, to use methods effectively, to use tools successfully;

c) informational competence - searching for, collecting, sorting, processing necessary, important, necessary, useful information in the information environment and using it purposefully, appropriately, and effectively;

d) creative competence - a critical and creative approach to pedagogical activities, the ability to demonstrate one's own creative skills;

e) innovative competence - putting forward new ideas on improving the pedagogical process, improving the quality of education, increasing the effectiveness of the educational process, and successfully implementing them into practice;

f) communicative competence - the ability to communicate sincerely with all participants of the educational process, including students, to listen to them, to have a positive influence on them;

g) personal competence - consistently achieving professional growth, increasing the level of qualifications, demonstrating one's internal capabilities in professional activity;

h) technological competence - assimilation of advanced technologies, modern tools, and techniques that enrich professional pedagogical knowledge, skills and competence, and access to technology. [2].

Extreme competence is the ability to make rational decisions and act correctly in emergency situations (natural disasters, technological process failure) when pedagogical conflicts arise.

In a number of studies, professional competence specific to a pedagogue and its specific aspects have been studied. Among such studies, it is possible to include the research conducted by A.K. Markova and B. Nazarova.

In the research conducted by A.K. Markova, it was stated that the professional competence of the pedagogue consists of the following structural foundations:

Special or professional competence (organization of professional activity at a high level);

Social competence (organization of additional activities in cooperation);

Personal competence (self-development, self-expression);

Individual competence (self-management, professional development and creating news).

The implementation of the competence approach in educational practice requires a deep and comprehensive scientific study of all aspects of this process. At the same time, it should be noted that it is difficult to interpret competence as a pedagogical phenomenon because the category of competence was introduced into pedagogy from other disciplines, it is sufficiently deeply understood and has a strong place in the sciences. As a result of new socio-economic processes, it entered the content of the concepts of pedagogy relatively recently, and for now, it fully belongs to the system of pedagogical, especially didactic concepts.

At the same time, due to the relevance of competency-oriented approaches in education, the terms "competence", "competence", "basic competencies" are increasingly used in the discussion of issues related to the new qualities of education and are becoming more and more widespread. In the pedagogical community, the process of understanding competences and competencies, which of them are considered basic (universal), and what are the methods of their formation and evaluation is gaining momentum, intense discussions on clarifying these concepts are ongoing. Therefore, today there are many definitions and interpretations of these concepts.

Competence means not only the presence and significant amount of acquired knowledge and experience, but also the ability to use them at the right time and use them in the course of performing one's official duties.

In this sense, competence is a description of a person, a person, a professional, at the same time, it is a sum of the personal capabilities of a person, his ability to effectively use his professional knowledge and experience in his practical activities. Competence as a description of the specialist's ability to perform effective professional activity has become the basis of the competence approach in education. Emphasizing the complex, integral nature of such competence, its three levels are distinguished in management models abroad:

1) Integrative competence - the ability to collect knowledge and skills and use them in the rapidly changing conditions of the external environment.

2) Socio-psychological competence - intelligence, knowledge, and skills to understand people's behavior, motivation of their activities, high level of openness and communication culture.

3) Competence in certain areas of management activity - decision-making, information gathering, methods of working with people, etc.

Components of competence develop and manifest only in the process of performing activities that are interesting for a person. Effective performance resulting from several factors depends much more on a series of independent and interchangeable competencies that cover a wide range of situations in the course of action aimed at achieving a goal, than on the level of competence or ability that is obtained separately, manifested in a specific situation. will be liq.

In the assessment of competence, it is necessary to consider not a single level of competence, but a complete set of competencies manifested in various situations during a long period of time spent by a person to achieve personally important goals. In this case, the specific situation faced by a person has a direct impact on his development, the formation of values, and the acquisition of new competencies.

Realizing the diversity of the field of competencies, which are important to acquire for a professional activity to be effective, caused the problem of determining

the scope of these competencies, as well as distinguishing among them the most universal basic competencies.

Today, there are various classifications of basic competencies in world education. M. Stobart basic competence identified the following five groups of them:

1) Political and social competencies (for example, taking responsibility, participating in joint decision-making, resolving conflicts through compromise, and participating in the activities of democratic institutions);

2) Competencies related to the life of a multicultural society (for example, correct understanding of differences, respect for each other, living in harmony with people who have acquired other cultures, languages and religious beliefs);

3) Competencies related to the ability to carry out oral and written communication (for example, mastering several languages);

4) Competencies related to the emergence of information society (for example, mastering new technologies, being able to use them, being able to have a critical attitude towards information and advertisements distributed through mass media channels);

5) Competence to learn professionally and personally throughout life as the basis of continuous education.

The last competence is of particular importance, so some researchers call it systemic competence. Ye.P. Tonkonogaya

and V. Yu. The Krichevskys, who consider the personal qualities that have gained professional importance, put competence on a par with ethics, pedagogic organization, management, communication, and other qualities.

Competence itself is the breadth of the pedagogue's general outlook and high culture, pedagogy, psychology, management theory and the existence of professional knowledge on the scientific foundations of education management, the ability to develop their knowledge in practice, social and knowledge of the methods of psychological-pedagogical research, the ability to acquire the necessary set of pedagogical and management skills. In other words, competence is determined by the availability of professional knowledge and skills, as well as the ability to apply and improve them in practical activities.

In the works of pedagogues-scientists, various aspects and components that allow a wider and more detailed study of competence from a pedagogical point of view have been isolated and studied. S.Y.E. Shishov gives the following definitions of competence:

general competence based on knowledge, experience, values and inclinations acquired through study;

the ability to establish a connection between knowledge and situations, to find a suitable solution to a problem (it is permissible to say competence only if it is

demonstrated in a situation, unmanifested competence is not competence, but hidden possibilities are a big deal even if it gets lost).

L.M. Dolgova, P.V. According to Simonov and others, competence means being able to act based on acquired knowledge. In contrast to "knowledge, skills and competencies" which imply actions similar to patterns, competence implies the experience of independent action based on universal knowledge. "Competence is the presence of knowledge and skills in the form of social practice, which is manifested in cases where socio-cultural requirements and demands are imposed by society on the results of the educational process," says L.M. Dolgova.

V.V. According to Bashev, competencies are the individual abilities of a person, which are manifested in the ability to transfer this ability to other conditions when the conditions change. Fields of application determine their specificity and accuracy (mathematical, linguistic, political and other competencies).

A person who works effectively in the field of social studies should be able to:

- 1) to be able to research the situation he finds himself in;
- 2) being able to communicate with other people;
- 3) ability to make decisions;
- 4) able to organize individual and collective actions for the implementation of the adopted decisions;
- 5) ability to acquire new methods of activity.

Thus, competence is the ability, readiness, ability

and at the same time, it can be interpreted as the result of certain actions. In other words, competence is a category related to activity, which is manifested in the course of professional, social and other activities of the subject aimed at fulfilling the assigned tasks. If we define it in a more generalized way, competence is the surrounding objects necessary for an individual to carry out successful activities in society in general and in the professional field in particular.

and it means a certain level of formation of certain skills and professional experience in cooperation with subjects. [4].

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